

Unintended pregnancy among older married women of reproductive age in a city in Southwest Nigeria: A household-based study

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Abstract

Introduction: Unintended pregnancies constitute one of the major public health problems of important concern in Nigeria, where sex refusal in marriage might be impossible. This descriptive household-based study investigated the prevalence and predictors of unintended pregnancy in the past two years among married women aged 35-49 years in Ibadan, South West, Nigeria.

Methods: A three-stage sampling technique was used to recruit 425 respondents across three local government areas. Data were collected and analyzed using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire. The dependent variable, "Unintended pregnancy," was defined as an unplanned, unwanted, or mistimed pregnancy. Data were summarized using descriptive statistics. Bivariate chi-square tests were used to determine the factors associated with unintended pregnancy, while binary logistic regression was used to determine the predictors of unintended pregnancy ($\alpha 0.05$).

Results: The mean age of the women was 41.1 ± 4.2 years, 149 (35.1%) had high autonomy, while 233 (54.8%) had medium autonomy. Further, 177 (41.6%) were poor, while 106 (25.0%) were rich. In all, 108 (25.4%) women have had an unintended pregnancy. Women with low autonomy (AOR=3.41, 95%CI=1.70-6.82, $p=0.001$) and medium autonomy (AOR=2.41, CI=1.29-4.49, $p=0.006$) had higher odds of unintended pregnancy. The likelihood of unintended pregnancy was higher among women living in poor households (AOR=2.04, 95%CI=1.13-3.68, $p=0.017$).

Conclusions: The level of unintended pregnancy was high among older women of reproductive age in Ibadan. Social interventions that focus on empowerment of such women should be undertaken by governmental agencies, non-governmental agencies, and community-based organizations to increase women's autonomy and reduce unintended pregnancy among them.

Take-home message: We found that one out of every four married women aged 35-49 years have had an unintended pregnancy in the past two years. The factors responsible were: Having more than three children, previous use of a family planning method, poverty, and lack of independence in making decisions about the woman's own health.

Keywords: abortion; contraceptive use; Ibadan; older married women; unintended pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION

Unintended pregnancies are pregnancies that are either mistimed, unplanned, or unwanted at the time of conception [1]. It is one of the major public health problems of important concern in Nigeria, where sex refusal in marriage might be impossible. Unintended pregnancy is strongly associated with negative physical, social, mental, and economic outcomes [2]. Unintended pregnancies do not just occur among the young, poor, uneducated, rural dwellers, or the unmarried, it also affects the rich, educated, urban dwellers, and married individuals and is one of the drivers of maternal and infant mortality in Nigeria [3,4]. Worldwide, the prevalence of unintended pregnancies had been reported to be substantially higher in developing countries compared to developed countries [5].

Annually, an estimated 208 million pregnancies occur globally, with 46% of them being unintended, and more than 14 million unintended pregnancies have been reported in Sub-Saharan Africa [6,7]. Although the global trend of unintended pregnancy has decreased over time, it remains high with significant regional variations. In 2011, the percentages of unintended pregnancies resulting in birth were 33% for African American women, 31% for Hispanic women, and 17% for Caucasian women in the United States [8]. Analyzing data from the National Survey of Family Growth spanning from 2006 to 2010, Kim and colleagues found that 50% of the 3577 pregnancies were unintended [9]. In Canada, three out of every 10 pregnancies were unintended and the rates were higher among residents in the Northern territories (33.6%) compared to those in the Western-British Columbia (25.8%) [10]. About 16% and 19% of married women living in England and Asia have had an unintended pregnancy respectively [11,12]. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the prevalence of unintended pregnancy was 29%, ranging from 10.8% in Nigeria to 54.5% in Namibia [13]. In Ibadan, Southwest Nigeria, 21.8% married women aged 15-49 years who have been married for at least one year and with a living child have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage [14].

Unintended pregnancies commonly result from contraceptive failure, incorrect or non-use of contraceptives, and reliance on traditional family planning [15]. Multiple studies have shown other variables that influence the likelihood of unintended pregnancies including preference for sons, completed family size, and lack of spousal's economic support [16-18]. It's been reported that poor married women are more likely to have unprotected sexual intercourse than their counterparts who are rich and even when they use contraceptives, they have higher risks of contraceptive failure [19]. Moreover, poverty often results in lower levels of education and limited access to health information, which in turn leads to limited knowledge of pregnancy risks, contraceptive methods, and reproductive health needs. These factors may contribute to a higher burden of unwanted pregnancy that may end up in induced abortion. Despite a marginal increase

in the proportion of married women using modern contraceptives in Nigeria - from 7% in 2003 to 12% in 2018, an increasing trend of hospitalization of married women due to complications of induced abortion that resulted from unintended pregnancy has been observed in Ile-Ife, Nigeria [20-22]. Findings from a cross-sectional study conducted in Southwest Nigeria reported that married women constituted 30.2% of abortion seekers [22]. It has also been documented that married women may consider a pregnancy as unintended if it did not meet their childbearing goals such as spacing or limiting births [14,22].

The inability of family planning programmes to meet the contraceptive needs of married women who are at risk of unintended pregnancies may underline the high rates of unintended pregnancies in Nigeria. Previous research work has shown that married women contributed significantly to the overall burden of induced abortion in Nigeria [22], but there is need for more knowledge on the determinants of unintended pregnancies that may result in induced abortion amongst older married women most of which must have completed their family size. The need for current knowledge about the prevalence of unintended pregnancy among older married women in Ibadan is imperative as there exists limited publicly available information on the subject matter. About 33% of women in Ibadan are aged 35-49 years [23]. This a large proportion of the population, and they have reproductive health needs that may be unique to their group which are worth investigating. A study of this nature will help to estimate the prevalence of unintended pregnancy and identify strategies to bridge address it among older married women of reproductive age in Ibadan and by extension Nigeria. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the prevalence and predictors of unintended pregnancy among older married women of reproductive age in Ibadan, South West Nigeria.

METHODS

Study design and population target

This was a descriptive cross-sectional household-based study. This research was carried out in Ibadan, Oyo State, situated in the southwestern region of Nigeria. Ibadan ranks as the third largest city in Nigeria by population and holds the distinction of being the largest in terms of geographical expanse [24]. Ibadan comprises 11 Local Government Areas (LGAs), encompassing urban, semi-urban, and rural zones.²⁴ As of 2023, the estimated population of Ibadan stood at around 3.88 million within Nigeria's total population of 226 million.²⁴ While predominantly inhabited by the Yoruba ethnic group, Ibadan also accommodates a rich mix of other ethnicities, such as Igbo, Hausa, Edo, Ibibio, among others [24]. The study population included currently married women aged 35-49 years. Married women who had separated (temporarily or permanently) at the period of the survey were excluded.

Sampling procedure and study instruments

A three-stage sampling technique was employed to recruit eligible respondents (n=481). Initially, we utilized simple random sampling technique to select three out of the 11 LGAs in Ibadan. Subsequently, in the second stage, we selected five Enumeration Areas (EAs) from each of the previously chosen LGAs. A household listing of eligible respondents was then conducted across all selected EAs, forming the sampling frame for the study. The sample size for the study was determined using Leshlie Kish's formula, specifically designed for calculating sample sizes in cross-sectional studies.

A pretested interviewer-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire contains five sections, namely, sociodemographic characteristics, obstetric history, autonomy in decision-making about the woman's health, and occurrence of unintended pregnancy in the past two years prior the date of data collection in October 2022.

The outcome variable was unintended pregnancy in marriage and was assessed using three questions: "Have you ever had an unwanted pregnancy in this marriage in the past 2 years?", "Have you ever had a mistimed pregnancy in this marriage?", and "Have you ever had an unplanned pregnancy in this marriage?" Unintended pregnancy was defined as a history of unwanted pregnancy, mistimed pregnancy, or unplanned pregnancy in respondents' marriages. Responses were

dichotomized into “1 = Yes”, that is, an unintended pregnancy has occurred and “2 = No”, which implied that an unintended pregnancy has not occurred.

Predictor variables considered in this study included woman’s age (35-39, 40-44, and 45-49); age at marriage (<25, 25-27, \geq 28); place of residence (urban, rural); family type (monogamy, polygamy); woman’s highest educational attainment (at most primary, secondary, and higher); number of living children (<3, 3, >3); Woman’s occupation type (unemployed, unskilled manual, skilled manual, professional/technical/managerial, and clerical), history of contraceptive use (yes or no); wealth index. The wealth index was generated using the list of household items adopted from the 2018 NDHS dataset [21], and included details on electricity, radio, refrigerator, bicycle, motorcycle, car/truck, telephone, bank account, the main cooking fuel, main floor material of the house, main wall material of the house, and main roof material of the house. The wealth index was developed using Principal Components Analysis (PCA) on SPSS.25 The input to the PCA included the previously listed household items. A weight or factor score produced by principal components analysis was assigned to each family asset for which data was obtained. The obtained asset scores were standardized against a normal distribution with mean zero and standard deviation one. The distribution cut points that determined the wealth tertiles were then established using these standardized scores. The tertiles were arranged from poor, middle, and rich.); autonomy in decision-making about a woman’s healthcare was assessed using one question, “Who makes decisions about your (woman’s) healthcare?” was obtained from the 2018 NDHS dataset [21], and response to the question was graded from “1 = respondent alone; 2 = respondent and husband/partner; 3 = husband/partner alone; 4 = someone else; and 5 = other”. The responses to the autonomy question were further recoded into another variable with three options: “high autonomy=1” for women whose response option was “1”, “medium autonomy = 2” for those who selected option “2”, while “low autonomy = 3” was assigned to those whose response options were “3, 4, and 5”.); husband’s age, (35-39, 40-44, and 45+); husband’s level of education (no education, primary, secondary/higher), and husband’s occupation (unskilled manual, skilled manual, sales and services, professional/technical/managerial, and others); and pregnancy termination. This was defined as a positive response to the question: “What was the outcome of the unintended pregnancy: “Aborted = 1, “Stillbirth = 2, and Live birth = 3”. Respondents who selected response option “1”, which is aborted, were said to have terminated a pregnancy).

Statistical analysis

Data were summarized using SPSS version 25.0 [25] and in three stages. In the first stage of analysis, we did a descriptive summary (either as percentages for categorical variables or mean for continuous variables) of the factors. In the second stage, the factors associated with unintended pregnancy were assessed by the selected characteristics using Chi-square tests. The findings at this point demonstrated the individual impact of exogenous variables on the endogenous variables. The purpose of this level was to identify variables to be pooled into the multivariate analysis. The levels of statistical significance were set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical aspects

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Oyo State Research Ethics Committee (Reference No: AD 13/479/44594, and Date of approval: 05/10/2022). Informed consent was obtained from all respondents involved in the study.

RESULTS

A total of 425 women responded to the survey, and this yielded a response rate of 88.4%. Overall, the mean age of the women was 41.1 ± 4.2 years and the mean age at marriage was 25.4 ± 3.5 years. The mean number of living children was 3.2 ± 1.2 , while the mean number of desired children was 3.9 ± 1.5 ; the average number of males desired was 1.8 ± 0.4 , while the mean number of females desired was 1.7 ± 0.4 . Among the studied women, 276 (64.9%) lived in urban settings,

219 (51.5%) belonged to polygamous families, 233 (54.8%) had ever used contraceptives, 233 (54.8%) had medium autonomy, and 149 (35.1%) had high autonomy (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of married women enrolled from selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.

	Characteristics	Frequency	%
Age	35 - 39	161	37.9
	40 - 44	147	34.6
	45 - 49	117	27.5
	<25	160	37.6
Age at marriage	25 -27	155	36.5
	28 and above	110	25.9
Place of residence	Urban	276	64.9
	Rural	149	35.1
Family type	Monogamy	206	48.5
	Polygamy	219	51.5
	At most primary	75	17.6
Woman's highest educational attainment	Secondary	256	60.2
	Tertiary	94	22.1
Number of male children alive	≤3	255	60.0
	>3	170	40.0
Number of female children alive	≤3	406	95.5
	>3	19	4.5
Desired number of female children	≤3	53	12.5
	>3	372	87.5
Desired number of male children	≤3	413	97.2
	>3	12	2.8
Desired number of female children	≤3	415	97.6
	>3	10	2.4
Woman's occupation type	Unemployed	20	4.7
	Unskilled manual	95	22.4
	Skilled manual	149	35.1
	Professional/Technical/Managerial	104	24.5
	Clerical	57	13.4
Ever used contraceptives	Yes	233	54.8
	No	192	45.2
Wealth tertile	Poor	177	41.6
	Middle	142	33.4
	Rich	106	25.0
Autonomy in making decisions on woman's own healthcare	Low autonomy	43	10.1
	Medium autonomy	233	54.8
	High autonomy	149	35.1

Husband's highest educational attainment	At most primary	58	13.6
	Secondary	251	59.1
	Tertiary	116	27.3
Husband's current employment type	Unskilled manual	66	15.5
	Skilled manual	151	35.5
	Sales and services	95	22.4
Ever used contraceptives	Professional/Technical/Managerial	82	19.3
	Others	31	7.3
	Yes	233	54.8
Wealth tertile	No	192	45.2
	Poor	177	41.6
	Middle	142	33.4
Autonomy in making decisions on woman's own healthcare	Rich	106	25.0
	Low autonomy	43	10.1
	Medium autonomy	233	54.8
Husband's highest educational attainment	High autonomy	149	35.1
	At most primary	58	13.6
	Secondary	251	59.1
Husband's current employment type	Tertiary	116	27.3
	Unskilled manual	66	15.5
	Skilled manual	151	35.5
Ever used contraceptives	Sales and services	95	22.4
	Professional/Technical/Managerial	82	19.3

Overall, 233 (54.8%) of the older married women have used at least one contraceptive method in the past two years; 88 (37.8%) had used injectables only, 55 (23.6%) had used an intrauterine device only, and 29 (12.4%) had used pills only.

Figure 1. Contraceptive prevalence rate among older married women in selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.

In all, 108 (25.4%) older women aged 35 – 49 years have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years, out of whom 65 (60.0%) had an unwanted pregnancy, 27 (25.0%) had an unplanned pregnancy, and 16 (15.0%) had a mistimed pregnancy (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Prevalence of unintended pregnancy and its subtypes among married women aged 35-49 years in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Out of the women who have had an unintended pregnancy, 7.4% had procured an abortion in the past two years. Thirty-four women aged 35 – 39 years have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years compared to 42 (28.6%) aged 40 – 44 years, and 32 (27.4%) aged 45 years and above (Chi-square = 2.57, $p = 0.276$). Also, 15 (12.7%) married women who had <3 living children have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years compared to 37 (25.5%) with three living children, and 56 (34.6%) with >3 living children (Chi-square = 17.21, $p < 0.001$).

Furthermore, 76 (32.6%) women who have ever used contraceptives have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years compared to 32 (16.7%) with no history of contraceptive use (Chi-square = 14.13, $p < 0.001$). In

addition, 13 (30.2%) women with low autonomy have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years compared to 59 (39.6%) with medium autonomy and 36 (15.5%) with high autonomy (Chi-square = 28.54, $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Factors associated with recent event of unintended pregnancy among older married women living in selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Characteristics	Have had an unintended pregnancy		Chi-square	p-value	
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)			
Age	35 - 39	34 (21.1)	127 (78.9)	2.57	0.276
	40 - 44	42 (28.6)	105 (71.4)		
	45 - 49	32 (27.4)	85 (72.6)		
Age at marriage	<25	47 (29.4)	113 (70.6)	6.52	0.038*
	25 -27	43 (27.7)	112 (72.3)		
	28 and above	18 (16.4)	92 (83.6)		
Place of residence	Urban	65 (23.6)	211 (76.4)		
	Rural	43 (28.9)	106 (71.1)		
Family type	Monogamy				
	Polygamy				
Woman's highest educational attainment	At most primary	28 (37.3)	47 (62.7)	8.37	0.015*
	Secondary	63 (24.6)	193 (75.4)		
	Tertiary	17 (18.1)	77 (81.9)		
Number of male children alive	≤3	61 (23.9)	194 (76.1)	0.75	0.387
	>3	47 (27.6)	123 (72.4)		
Number of female children alive	≤3	99 (24.4)	307 (75.6)	5.06	0.025*
	>3	9 (47.4)	10 (52.6)		
Desired number of male children	≤3	104 (25.2)	309 (74.8)	0.41	0.762
	>3	4 (33.3)	8 (66.7)		
Desired number of female children	≤3	105 (25.3)	310 (74.7)	0.11	0.736
	>3	3 (30.0)	7 (70.0)		
Woman's occupation type	Unemployed	8 (40.0)	12 (60.0)	5.03	0.284
	Unskilled manual	23 (24.2)	72 (75.8)		
	Skilled manual	34 (22.8)	115 (77.2)		
	Professional/Technical/Managerial	24 (23.1)	80 (76.9)		
	Clerical	19 (33.3)	38 (66.7)		
Ever used contraceptives	Yes	76 (32.6)	157 (67.4)	14.13	<0.001*
	No	32 (16.7)	160 (83.3)		
Wealth tertile	Poor	60 (33.9)	117 (66.1)	12.58	0.002*
	Middle	24 (16.9)	118 (83.1)		
	Rich	24 (22.6)	82 (77.4)		

Autonomy in making decisions on woman's own healthcare	Low autonomy	13 (30.2)	30 (69.8)	28.54	<0.001*
	Medium autonomy	36 (15.5)	197 (84.5)		
	High autonomy	59 (39.6)	90 (60.4)		
Husband's highest educational attainment	At most primary	17 (29.3)	41 (70.7)	1.05	0.593
	Secondary	65 (25.9)	186 (74.1)		
	Tertiary	26 (22.4)	90 (77.6)		
	Unskilled manual	11 (16.7)	55 (83.3)		
Husband's current employment type	Skilled manual	47 (31.1)	104 (68.9)	6.21	0.184
	Sales and services	22 (23.2)	73 (76.8)		
	Professional/Technical/Managerial	22 (26.8)	60 (73.2)		
	Others	6 (19.4)	25 (80.6)		

Compared to older women with <3 living children, those with three children had twice higher odds of unintended pregnancy (aOR = 2.35, 95%CI = 1.18 – 4.69, p = 0.015), and those with >3 living children had more than three times higher odds of unintended pregnancy in their marriage in the past two years (aOR = 3.12, 95%CI = 1.61 – 6.04, p = 0.001). Older women who have ever used contraceptives had approximately three times higher odds of unintended pregnancy in their marriage in the past two years compared to those with no history of contraceptive use (aOR = 2.58, 95%CI = 1.55 – 4.28, p = <0.001). Compared to older women with low autonomy, those with high autonomy having twice higher odds of unintended pregnancy in their marriage over the past two years (aOR = 1.54, 95%CI = 0.72 – 3.33, p = 0.369), and those with medium autonomy had 63% less odds of unintended pregnancy in their marriage (aOR = 0.37, 95%CI = 0.17 – 0.80, p = 0.012) (Table 3).

Table 3. Predictors of unintended pregnancy among older married women living in selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Background Characteristics	Model 1			Model 2				
	uOR	95% C.I		p-value	aOR	95% C.I		p-value
		Lower	Upper			Lower	Upper	
Age								
35 – 39	1.13	0.59	2.15	0.711				
40-44	1.40	0.76	2.57	0.279				
45 and above	1							
Age at first marriage								
<25	1.37	0.77	2.43	0.279				
25 -27	0.83	0.41	1.70	0.609				
28 and above	1							
Place of residence								
Urban	0.80	0.48	1.33	0.386				
Rural	1							
Family type								
Monogamy	1.01	0.61	1.67	0.965				
Polygamy	1							
Woman's highest educational attainment								
At most Primary	1.52	0.66	3.52	0.331				

Secondary	1.10	0.55	2.19	0.786				
Tertiary	1							
Number of male children alive								
≤3	0.81	0.52	1.27	0.363				
>3	1							
Number of female children alive								
≤3	1				1			
>3	2.84	1.09	7.41	0.033*	2.87	1.21	7.65	0.043*
Desired number of male children								
≤3	0.62	0.16	2.47	0.499				
>3	1							
Desired number of female children								
≤3	1.36	0.28	6.74	0.705				
>3	1							
Woman's occupation type								
Unemployed	1.05	0.31	3.61	0.937				
Unskilled manual	0.52	0.21	1.24	0.140				
Skilled manual	0.57	0.26	1.26	0.166				
Prof./Technical/Managerial	0.50	0.21	1.19	0.117				
Clerical	1							
Ever used contraceptives								
Yes	2.74	1.60	4.69	<0.001*	2.58	1.55	4.28	<0.001*
No	1				1			
Wealth tertile								
Poor	1.95	1.01	3.76	0.045*	2.04	1.13	3.68	0.017*
Middle	1.63	0.71	3.75	0.252	1.19	0.56	2.52	0.648
Rich	1				1			
Autonomy in making decisions on woman's own healthcare								
Low autonomy	3.28	1.59	6.77	0.001*	3.41	1.70	6.82	0.001*
Medium autonomy	2.71	1.42	5.18	0.003*	2.41	1.29	4.49	0.006*
High autonomy	1				1			
Husband's highest educational attainment								
At most primary	1.16	0.40	3.34	0.780				
Secondary	0.94	0.44	2.02	0.879				
Tertiary	1							
Husband's current employment type								
Unskilled manual	1				1			
Skilled manual	2.94	1.19	7.23	0.019*	2.16	0.98	4.75	0.057
Sales and services	2.02	0.77	5.28	0.153	1.49	0.63	3.52	0.365
Professional/Technical/Managerial	3.63	1.21	10.9	0.022*	2.15	0.89	5.19	0.091

Others	1.44	0.40	5.13	0.578	1.40	0.42	4.59	0.584
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Note: * P < 0.05

DISCUSSION

From this study, we found that one out of every four (25.4%) married women aged 35 – 49 years have had an unintended pregnancy in their marriage in the past two years. This finding was at variance with findings from the pooled analysis of data from NDHS 2003-2013 which reported unintended pregnancy rates ranging from 3.8% - 15% among women aged 35-49 years [26]. Our findings also differ from the results of an analysis of the 2016 Uganda Demographic Health Survey which reported 44.5% prevalence of unintended pregnancy among women aged 15 – 49 years [27]. The differences in the prevalence of unintended pregnancies between our study and these literature could be due to differences in the study population and periods during which the studies were conducted. Our study underscores a significant aspect of reproductive health by bringing to light the high prevalence of occurrence of unintended pregnancies within marriages, an often-overlooked aspect of public health challenge. The lockdown implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic could possibly be the reason for the high level of unintended pregnancy that was observed in this study. Despite the high prevalence of unintended pregnancies in marriage found in this study, 7.4% of the women who had an unintended pregnancy procured an abortion. The prevalence of abortion found in this study is less than that reported from a cross-sectional study conducted among married antenatal clinic attendees in a tertiary institution in Nigeria who have had an unintended pregnancy (23.4%) married antenatal clinic attendees in a tertiary institution in Nigeria [28]. Given the social, religious, and cultural context in which this study was conducted, it is not surprising that only a few women opted for abortion services since the pregnancy was not intended. Furthermore, husbands of older women may have considered it less of an emotional burden to keep an unintended pregnancy rather than to permit their wives to undergo an abortion [29]. The perception of the risks of the health consequences of abortion could have dissuaded the couple from opting for abortion.

From this study, we found that unintended pregnancy was higher among women that had ever used contraceptives compared to those with no history of contraceptive use. A systematic review and meta-analysis reported that the pooled prevalence of unintended pregnancy among contraceptive users in low- and middle-income countries was 44.68% [30]. Another study conducted in 12 low and middle-income countries reported a pooled prevalence of 86.8% for unintended pregnancies.³¹ The observed inconsistency between studies can be alluded to differences in the population and geographical location. Specifically, our current research focused on women in Ibadan, Nigeria, while cited literature targeted women living in many low- and middle-income countries. The disparity can also be attributed to the differences in the age groups of women studied. Our results could also be attributed to the fact that as women age, their desire to become pregnant is likely to reduce.

In the present study, more than one-half of women used contraceptives, including pills, injectables, intrauterine devices, and implants. These methods have been reported among contraceptive users in Nigeria, Uganda, and other low middle-income countries [14,30-32]. The possibility that women who had experienced unintended pregnancy might have opted for contraceptive after such experience could be a possible explanation to this finding. It is also likely that the contraceptives used may not have been entirely effective in preventing unwanted pregnancies or complications. The reduced effectiveness of contraceptives could be an outfall of issues with the quality of healthcare services, especially access to reliable contraceptives [32,33]. In addition, the competency skills of family planning (FP) providers in providing contraceptives, especially the long-acting reversible contraceptives, and the ability to provide clients with comprehensive and balanced counseling may be suboptimal and need to be scaled up [34]. Some non-governmental organizations including MSI Nigeria Reproductive Choices and Society for Family Health, have been supporting the Federal Ministry of Health in Nigeria with capacity-building trainings for FP providers [35,36], however, there is more yet to be done.

From this study, we observed that wealth status was a significant predictor of unintended pregnancy among older married women. Women in the middle and poor wealth tertiles had higher odds of unintended pregnancy compared to those in the rich class. Women from lower wealth tertiles may face barriers in accessing quality healthcare services, including FP resources and education. Limited financial resources could hinder their ability to afford contraceptives or access healthcare facilities where FP services are available [37]. Previous research on socioeconomic inequalities in contraceptive use and method choice in Ghana, Nigeria, and Zambia shed light on disparities in contraceptive access based on socioeconomic status [38-40]. Women with greater financial resources may have more opportunities for education and employment, enabling them to make informed choices about their reproductive health.

Socioeconomic status intersects with cultural norms and gender dynamics, impacting women's autonomy and agency in reproductive decision-making [41]. Women from lower wealth tertiles may have less control over their reproductive choices due to patriarchal structures or societal expectations. Addressing gender disparities and promoting women's empowerment is crucial in reducing unintended pregnancies. Financial constraints could deter women from seeking regular reproductive healthcare services, leading to unintended pregnancies due to lack of access to contraceptives or FP counseling [41].

From this study, we found that women with low or medium autonomy had higher odds of unintended pregnancy compared to those with high autonomy. Similarly, studies conducted in Ethiopia and Bangladesh [42-44] found that women who decided independently to use contraception (high autonomy) had lower odds of unintended pregnancy than women who decided jointly with their husbands (medium autonomy) or by their husbands alone (low autonomy). The agreement between our findings and literature emphasizes the role women's autonomy plays in reducing the rate of unintended pregnancies.

Policy implications

To reduce the occurrence of unintended pregnancies among women aged 35-49 years in Ibadan, Nigeria, stakeholders at the Ministries of Women Affairs, and Health and Social Welfare should work together to develop policies that advocate for women's economic empowerment and reproductive health rights. Also, hospital administrators and the Heads of Nursing and/or public health education should work together to integrate post-partum family planning into routine antenatal and immunization clinics.

Study limitations

This was a community-based quantitative study conducted among older married women only. Focus group discussions with the women groups and/or in-depth interviews with the abortion clients would have provided more insights into events of unintended pregnancies among older women and their husbands.

CONCLUSIONS

The level of recent experience of unintended pregnancies was high among older married women of reproductive age in Ibadan, South West, Nigeria. The significance of contraceptive use, wealth status, and autonomy as predictors of unintended pregnancy among older married women underscores the complex interplay between socioeconomic factors, healthcare access and utilization, education, and cultural norms. Addressing disparities in access to reproductive healthcare services and promoting women's empowerment are critical in reducing unintended pregnancies among older married women in Ibadan and similar parts of Nigeria. Policies aimed at reducing the financial burden of healthcare services, particularly for marginalized groups, are essential in addressing disparities in unintended pregnancies. In addition, social interventions that focus on empowerment for women and increase their autonomy should be prioritized in Ibadan, South West Nigeria.

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